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Short Communication

Primary detection of natural phenols from the stems used in teeth problems by the tribal communities of Bonai Forest Division, Odisha

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ABSTRACT

Tooth decay is a very common and universal problem throughout the world. There are a number of causes are identified. Allopathic medications are available to cure the problem related to toothache, but the side effects are also observed. People throughout the world are declining towards the organic products to cure the health problems. The traditional ethnomedicinal practices are available against teeth problems, but those are still unexplored with no side effects. Keeping the above problems and importance of traditional practices, an attempt has been made to document the stems used in teeth problems by the tribal communities of Bonai Forest Divisions, Odisha, India. The secondary metabolites present in enumerated stems might be responsible to cure teeth problems. Therefore, the primary detections of natural phenols are carried out in the field. The results revealed that the selected stems showed the presence of phenolic compounds. The present study provides a baseline data for further advanced experimental research works against teeth problems.

INTRODUCTION

Tooth decay has become one of the most common diseases found across the globe. It is a condition where the destruction of the enamel occurs. The microbes present in the mouth are responsible for making mouth acidic that causes attack to the enamel. The symptoms begin with the formation of dental plaque that has a sticky texture and changes the colour from pale yellow to brown. It has

been observed that the colour appears on all sides of the chewing teeth, on the surface of the gums or sometimes at the edge of the neck of the lower teeth. This process occurs as the result of a series of complex chemical reactions. As per the studies, it has been observed that mostly *Streptococcus mutans* cause tooth decay (Sahoo et al. 2021). Various allopathic medications are available for teeth decay, but side effects are reported. In order to avoid it people are moving towards the natural products as they have no side effects. Therefore, an attempt has been made to document the most common plants used to cure teeth problems by the tribal communities of Bonai Forest Division, Odisha. The plants might have some specific metabolites which are able to kill or inhibit the pathogenic microbes. To detect such types of plant parts in the field needs qualitative detections. So, the selection rate will be faster and more authenticated. Hence, primary detections of compounds in enumerated plant parts were also carried out in the present study.

METHODOLOGY

The ethnomedicinal survey was carried out in Bonai Forest Division from the month of November to December 2022. The information was collected from tribal people using questionnaires through interview and discussion. Three types of stems are selected for primary detection of bioactive compounds. As per the information given by tribal communities the stems of neem (*Azadirachta indica*), Sal (*Shorea robusta*) and Huhudi (*Vitex negundo*) were collected. 9 inches of stem were taken and one end of the stems were dipped in water. The stem of Huhudi was kept for 6 hours and the stems of Neem and Sal were kept for 12 hours. Then the froth observation was noted and pH of the samples were measured to know whether the sample was acidic or basic in nature. pH test was taken using litmus paper and the readings were noted (Plate 1).

Plate 1: Collection of information on stem of *Vitex negundo* and primary detection of phenolic compounds in the field

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ethnomedicinal survey was conducted in the Bonai Forest Division about the plant parts used against tooth decay. The results revealed that local people commonly used three plant species, *Azadirachta indica* (neem), *Shorea robusta* (Sal) and *Vitex negundo* (huhudi). The stem of Sal is used for brushing and the stem of Neem and Huhudi is used for anti-tooth decay. The experiment

showed that all the samples were acidic in nature (pH value approximately 6 or below) and it indicates that there might be the presence of the phenols. Phenols are responsible for killing the bacteria causing tooth decay. Badgular et al. (2008) reported that about 20 plants are used to cure oral problems from Nandurbar district of Maharashtra. Bairwa et al. (2012) reported about 12 plants are used for dental problems. Singh et al. (2013) reported about 29 plants are used for tooth decay from Sundargarh, Mayurbhanj, Bolangir and Angul districts of Odisha. Smith et al. (2017) reported that 62 plants are used to cure dental problems from Burkina Faso, West Africa. Sahoo et al. (2021) reported that about 16 plants are used to cure dental problems from Odisha, India. Sharma and Singh (2021) reported about 13 plants that are used to cure dental problems.

CONCLUSION

Teeth problems become a major and common problem all over the world. From the ethnomedicinal survey in Bonai Forest Division on tooth decay, it has been found that people are using *Azadirachta indica* (neem), *Shorea robusta* (sal), and *Vitex negundo* (huhudi) as tooth brush as they have anti-tooth decay properties. From the experiment, it was observed that all the samples are acidic in nature and it indicates that the presence of phenol which might be responsible for killing the pathogenic microbes. The stems of these plants can be used to clean the teeth as anti-tooth decay agent.

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